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Purchasing Behavior of Rural Consumers Migrated To Urban Areas: A Case Study of Sukkur and Khairpur Districts

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Abstract: - Many people migrate from rural areas to urban areas due to better infrastructure. Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants is described and influenced by five study variables which include Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB), Purchasing Consciousness (PC), Enjoy Purchasing (EP), Income/Pocket Money (INC/PM) and Price Consciousness / Quality Consciousness (PRC/ QC). This study is carried out as a Case Study of Sukkur and Khairpur districts in which an attempt has been made to understand the Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. A close ended survey was conducted from 383 respondents and data was analyzed by using Descriptive Statistics and Factor Analysis. Results of study suggest that rural migrants show Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) as they switch brands in urban market. Further study discloses that rural migrants show Purchasing Consciousness (PC) and they Enjoy Purchasing (EP) in urban market. Migrants also consider Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) on purchasing. Results also show that rural migrants have Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) in urban market.

Key Words: Consumers, Behavior, Switchover, Consciousness

1.0 Introduction

Purchasing Behavior is defined as a process that people adopt while they purchase and consume any product tangible or intangible and ideas with an ultimate object of satisfying the needs and wants (Kotler & Keller, 2011). There is an inequality of infrastructure, education and health facilities between cities and villages and this inequality becomes a major instinctive force for people living in rural areas to migrate to urban areas (Devadas & Manohar, 2011). They further added that there is sizeable number of people who are migrating from rural areas to urban areas in search for a better future, better job opportunities along with satisfactions of personal needs. Migration in Pakistan has increased about six times since independence (Karim & Nasar, 2009) due to better infrastructure and more facilities available.

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Purchasing Behavior has remained focus of study for urban and rural consumers or their comparison. Researchers have been working on Purchasing Behavior of urban consumers and rural consumers. The current study is conducted with a view to comprehend the Purchasing Behavior of migrant consumers regarding personal care products in Sukkur and Khairpur districts.

This study would help companies attract and retain migrated consumers by understanding factors affecting their Purchasing Behavior. By analyzing purchasing behavior a more comprehensive view of social aspect that migrants create by their decisions regarding purchasing behavior is identified as migrants becomes used of factors for taking purchasing behavior.

2.0 Research Problem

Rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas can constitute a good market if their Purchasing Behavior is completely studied in urban market environment which has not yet been (Devadas & Manohar 2011). There is a significant relation between people who migrate and their Purchasing Behavior (Chen et al, 2003). There is no significant study on Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who have migrated from their native places to urban area in Pakistan. It is necessary to comprehend the Purchasing Behavior of those consumers who are not urban consumers by birth. Research Problem for this study is to understand and chalk out the factors affecting Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts.

3.0 Study Objectives

This research study has following objectives.

- (1) To understand the Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts.
- (2) To describe factors effecting Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts.

4.0 Literature Review

Shih, Yu, and Tseng (2015) worked on Purchasing Behavior of consumers. They found that Purchasing Behavior of consumer is influenced by characteristics that a product possesses. Their study revealed that consumer Purchasing Behavior is affected and influenced by satisfaction of consumer with reference to product. They concluded with a finding that consumer purchases a product once consumer is satisfied with different characteristics and attributes of a product.

Joshi et al. (2012) in a study found out that rural consumers who have come to cities for study purposes are attracted by color, pricing and shape when they show their Purchasing Behavior on mobile phones. Their study can be considered a significant one in trying to identify different variables which are affecting a migrant consumer while they purchase any product. Pricing plays an important role while purchasing a product and above study concluded that migrants while showing Purchasing Behavior in cities become more Price conscious. Zameer et al. (2012) conducted their study on rural migrants and according to their study at the time of independence Pakistan was a country where two - third of the population was living in rural areas but this trend

has changed with passage of time. They further add that this change of trend has mainly occurred because cities have developed at rapid pace and have obtained infrastructural superiority. According to them cities and urban areas have more to offer in the field of employment, education and awareness forcing people to migrate. Devadas and Manohar (2011) worked on purchasing patterns and behavior that are shown by rural consumers who have migrated to urbanized environment in India According to them migrated consumers show Brand Switchover Behavior as they switch the brands in urban environment. Hamid (2010) found that there is an increase in rural to urban migration in Pakistan. Amanor-Boadu (2009) argued that rural migrant consumers focus on attractiveness of shops along with its location which creates consciousness to purchase in them. Sun and Wu (2004) conducted a study on urban and rural consumers. The objective of the study was to find out if there exists any similarity of Purchasing Behavior between urban and rural consumers. This study was conducted in China. They found out that there is no similarity in the behavior of urban and rural consumers as far as marketing mix is concerned and both consumers behave differently while they purchase the product. They further added that consumers focused on price and quality as they were worried about the price of products when they made their purchases and their qualitative structure. Lau-Gesk (2003) worked on consumer Purchasing Behavior and their research concluded that migrant consumer must involve income while showing Purchasing Behavior. He also worked on income with relevance to rural migrants and is of the opinion that migrants earn more income after migration and then they consider income or any other source available before purchasing at urban environment.

5.0 Study Model

Figure: 01

The study model for this study has been adopted and modified considering the “American consumer satisfaction index model (2009)” developed in University of Michigan’s Ross School of Business. This model is suggesting that Purchasing Behavior of migrants is affected by Brand Switchover Behavior, Purchasing Consciousness, Enjoy Purchasing, Income/ Pocket Money and Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness.

6.1 Methodology

Quantitative methodology has been used in this study to comprehend Purchasing Behavior of migrants in Sukkur and Khairpur districts. Population for the study contains Rural migrants who have spent three to ten years time in urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts and estimated population is 100000. Migrant Students who earn Income or receive Pocket Money from colleges (age ranges from 16 to above 20 years) of Sukkur and Khairpur districts have been taken as Sample and Convenient Sampling technique has been used. Sample size for the study is 383 determined on the basis of table given by (Saunders et al., 2009) and derived on formula given by (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). Adopted and modified questionnaire of (Devadas & Manohar, 2011) has been used to get responses.

6.2 Analysis and Results

Data has been analyzed using SPSS software.

6.3 Factor Analysis

Factor Analysis has been used to understand factors effecting Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants in Sukkur and Khairpur districts.

(a) Extraction of Factors

Figure: 02

Component	Total Variance Explained			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	Initial Eigenvalues % of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.640	17.599	17.599	2.640	17.599	17.599
2	2.261	15.074	32.672	2.261	15.074	32.672
3	1.656	11.037	43.710	1.656	11.037	43.710
4	1.513	10.088	53.798	1.513	10.088	53.798
5	1.253	8.352	62.149	1.253	8.352	62.149
6	.985	6.565	68.714			
7	.790	5.269	73.983			
8	.764	5.091	79.074			
9	.590	3.933	83.007			
10	.545	3.634	86.641			
11	.462	3.079	89.720			
12	.431	2.873	92.594			
13	.386	2.571	95.165			
14	.374	2.494	97.659			
15	.351	2.341	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Based on Eigen Values five factors were retained for further observation which explain Purchasing Behavior by 62.149%.

(b) Rotated Component Matrix using Varimax Rotation

Table: 01: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
BSB5	.724				
BSB2	.676				
BSB6	.632				
BSB1	.608				
BSB4	.595				
BSB3	.554				
EP2		.810			
EP3		.798			
EP1		.733			
INC/PM2			.871		
INC/PM1			.853		
PC1				.866	
PC2				.852	
PRCQC1					.883
PRCQC2					.856
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.					
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.					

Strong loadings on all items suggest that Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants is strongly affected by above five factors and items of these factors.

7.0 Study Hypotheses and their Acceptation/ Rejection

H:1: Rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts show Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) by switching brands in urban market:

Figure: 03

Result of Descriptive Analysis show that Rural Migrants have Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) with mean value of 3.56 suggesting that migrants have agreed that they show Brand

Switchover Behavior by switching brands in urban market. Further 61% of migrants have agreed that they show Brand Switchover Behavior by switching brands in urban market.

H:2: Rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts show Purchasing Consciousness (PC) while purchasing in urban market:

Figure: 04

Result of Descriptive Analysis show that Rural Migrants show Purchasing Consciousness (PC) with mean value of 3.61 suggesting that migrants have agreed that they show Purchasing Consciousness in urban market. Further 66% of migrants have agreed that they show Purchasing Consciousness in urban market.

H:3: Rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts Enjoy Purchasing (EP) while purchasing in urban market:

Figure: 05

Result of Descriptive Analysis show that Rural Migrants Enjoy Purchasing (EP) with mean value of 3.62 suggesting that migrants have agreed that they Enjoy Purchasing in urban market. Further 57% of migrants have agreed that they Enjoy Purchasing in urban market.

H:4: Rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts consider Income/pocket money (INC/PM) while purchasing in urban market:

Figure: 06

Result of Descriptive Analysis show that Rural Migrants have Income/Pocket Money (INC/PM) with mean value of 3.88 suggesting that migrants have agreed that they consider Income/Pocket Money before Purchasing in urban market. Further 79% of migrants have agreed that they consider Income/Pocket Money in urban market.

H:5: Rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts show Price/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) while purchasing in urban market:

Figure: 07

Result of Descriptive Analysis show that Rural Migrants have Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) with mean value of 3.50 suggesting that migrants have agreed that they purchase products of low price and good quality. Further 64.3% of migrants have agreed they purchase products of low price and good quality.

8.0 Conclusion

This study was intended to understand a very interesting aspect relating to purchasing behavior of rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. Results of the study have shown that Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts is affected by Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB), Purchasing Consciousness (PC), Enjoy Purchasing (EP), Income/Pocket Money (INC/PM) and Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC). This generally creates attraction for companies and organizations to focus on these factors and design suitable strategies to target these factors which affect Purchasing Behavior of rural consumers who have migrated to urban areas of Sukkur and Khairpur districts and achieve desirable results

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